

Questionnaire Of The Impact of the Fashion blogosphere on Gen-Z female consumers, and the implications for improved communication approaches

Dear respondents, firstly, I would like to thank you for participating in this questionnaire survey. I am a graduate student at the University of Manchester. I am conducting a research on the impact of fashion blogs on female Chinese consumer behavior for Generation Z. This questionnaire will provide data support for my research project and be used for the empirical investigation of my dissertation. This study follows the laws and regulations of data protection to protect your privacy. And your answers will be kept confidential and used for academic research only, and will not be provided to any third party. This project has been approved by the University of Manchester's research ethics program.

Thank you very much for taking the time to participate in this survey. There are 44 questions in this questionnaire, which will occupy 3 to 5 minutes to complete it.

If you have any doubt about this questionnaire, please contact me via my email address: yue.chang-4@postgrad.manchester.ac.uk

Before you start to take this questionnaire, please make sure that you are Chinese females aged between 18 and 24. This study is aimed at Chinese females aged 18-24. If you do not meet this requirement, you may not participate in this survey. Thank you for your cooperation.

Attention:

Fashion blogs are written by bloggers who are interested in fashion and they provide a variety of information with their followers, including fashion brands and products, fashion trends, e-commerce, personal style and street style.

Are you voluntary to participate in this questionnaire survey?

- A. Yes
- B. No

Part one Basic information

1. Your gender

- A. Female
- B. Male

2. Your age

- A. under 18
- B. 18-24
- C. 25-30
- D. over 30

3. Your education background

- A. High school and below
- B. Undergraduate
- C. Postgraduate
- D. Doctor and above

4. Where are you from

- A. China mainland
- B. China Hong Kong, Macao and Taiwan

5. Your occupation

- A. Student
- B. Company employee
- C. Self-employed person
- D. Freelancers
- E. Others

6. Your monthly disposable personal income(If you are a student, please choose your monthly living expense):
- A. Under 3000RMB
 - B. 3000-5000RMB
 - C. 5000-10000RMB
 - D. 10000-20000RMB
 - E. Over 20000RMB 20000
7. Do you follow fashion bloggers in social media
- A. Yes
 - B. No
8. Which social media do you use to follow fashion bloggers
- A. Weibo
 - B. Little Red Book
 - C. WeChat
 - D. Tiktok
 - E. Bilibili
 - F. Others
9. How much time do you spent browsing blogs per day
- A. Under 1 h
 - B. 1-2 h
 - C. 2-3 h
 - D. Over 3 h
10. The average frequency of browsing fashion blogs per week
- A. Under 3 times
 - B. 4-6 times
 - C. 7-9 times
 - D. Over 10 times

Please evaluate how much you agree with the following situations by using 1 to 5 scores

1= Strongly disagree; 2=Disagree; 3=Neutral; 4=Agree; 5=Strongly agree

Part two Dimensions of fashion blogging

Please think of a fashion blog you follow and answer the following questions

Entertainment

- E1. The contents of the fashion blog are interesting
- E2. I am relaxed and enjoyable when I browse the fashion blog
- E3. Following the fashion blogging can help me temporarily escape from daily chores

Interaction

- I1. The fashion blogger interacts with followers or readers frequently
- I2. It is easy and convenient to provide opinion through the fashion blog
- I3. I would like to communicate, discuss and exchange opinions with other readers in the fashion blog

Trendiness

- T1. The contents of the fashion blog are the latest and fashionable
- T2. I can search information of brands and products I need in the fashion blog
- T3. I use the contents of fashion blog as my inspiration

Credibility

- C1. I think the fashion blogger have enough expertise
- C2. The contents of the fashion blog are authentic, accurate and believable
- C3. The information of the fashion blog is impartial and free of personal bias

eWOM

W1. I am willing to get information and suggestion from the fashion blog

W2. I am willing to post information and suggestion on the fashion blog

W3. I am willing to pass contents from the fashion blog to my relatives and friends

Part three Factors in decision-making process

Consumers' cognition for brands (Brand Awareness & Brand Image)

When the fashion blog mentions the L brand(Such as LV, Gucci, Burberry...)

BW1. The characteristics of L brand come to my mind quickly

BW2.I will quickly recall the symbol and logo of L brand

BI1.I will quickly realize that brand L is a luxury brand

BI2.I will think the products image of L brand are fashionable and qualified

Consumers' attitude for brands (Brand Preference& Brand Loyalty)

When L brand is recommended by the fashion blog I follow

BP1. I prefer L brand, even if other brands have the same features as L

BP2. I prefer L brand, even if other brands are as good as L

BL1. I am willing to recommend L brand to others

BL2. L brand will be my first choice

Consumer purchase intention

When the products/brands emerge in fashion blogs/when fashion bloggers recommend products/brands

PI1. I will be interested in it.

PI2. I am willing to buy this product/brand rather than any others

PI3. I am willing to recommend others to buy this product/brand

PI4. I intend to purchase this product/brand in the future

Part four Purchase action

PA1. The contents and suggestions of the fashion blog are helpful to my purchase decision.

PA2. The contents and suggestions of the fashion blog will make me have real buying behavior.

PA3. I have bought products/brands recommended by fashion blogs.

PA4. The products/brands purchased according to the contents and suggestions of the fashion blog are generally satisfactory

PA5. Next time to buy products, I would also like to refer to the contents and suggestions of the fashion blog

Part five Suggestion

1. Your suggestions for this questionnaire
2. Your suggestions for fashion blogging